

Table: Projected global greenhouse gas emission levels by 2030 (31 January 2022)

Table S.4: Greenhouse gas emissions (including LULUCF) in G20 economies, selected non-G20 countries and global emission levels, projected for 2030 for the IMAGE current policies scenario, the unconditional NDC scenario and the conditional NDC scenario.

GHG emissions (MtCO ₂ eq)			Current policies scenario			Unconditional NDC scenario			Conditional NDC scenario		
	2005	2015	2030	min	max	2030	min	max	2030	min	max
Argentina	418	379	349	349	349	357	357	357	349	349	349
Australia	612	534	541	466	541	447	441	452	447	441	452
Brazil	2178	1373	1806	1183	1806	1511	1394	1627	1511	1394	1627
Canada	739	723	688	681	688	390	371	408	390	371	408
China	7150	11692	14530	12111	14530	13745	12010	14530	13745	12010	14530
EU27	4225	3516	2197	2197	2861	2085	2085	2085	2085	2085	2085
India	1650	2426	4170	4170	4466	5010	4929	5091	4445	4378	5091
Indonesia	1317	2404	2074	1886	2105	2037	2037	2037	1693	1693	1693
Japan	1289	1262	1017	863	1017	807	807	807	807	807	807
Mexico	605	724	774	759	836	773	773	773	634	634	634
Russia	1435	1447	1722	1345	1722	2161	2161	2161	1647	1647	1647
Saudi Arabia	417	640	984	933	1035	1034	854	1214	1034	854	1214
South Africa	497	550	472	432	472	385	350	420	385	350	420
South Korea	510	654	547	547	698	437	437	437	437	437	437
Turkey	263	376	446	446	594	928	928	928	928	928	928
United Kingdom	698	515	383	383	383	260	260	260	260	260	260
United States	6635	5907	4900	4900	5492	3251	3185	3317	3251	3185	3317
G20 economies	30,636	35,122	36,953	32,851	38,736	35,045	32,819	36,896	33,773	31,615	35,275
Chile	84		124	122	126	95	95	95	95	95	95
Colombia	245		296	283	309	169	169	169	169	169	169
DR Congo	211		370	361	378				340	340	340
Ethiopia	144		194	162	226	348	348	348	126	126	126
Kazakhstan	231		426	396	438	315	315	315	278	278	278
Morocco	62		100	78	121	116	116	116	78	78	78
Philippines	155		287	287	287				96	102	90
Thailand	305		481	481	481	444	444	444	416	416	416
Ukraine	408		405	384	414	309	309	309	309	309	309
Non-G20 countries	12,540	16,016	17,028	19,471	19,471	17,419	17,253	18,354	18,853	21,296	21,296
International bunker emissions	1,035	1,184	1,699	1,699	1,699	1,699	1,699	1,699	1,699	1,699	1,699
Remaining LULUCF CO ₂ emissions	886	678	744	744	744	744	744	744	744	744	744
Global, excluding the impact of	45,153	51,181	56,826	52,592	59,552	56,341	54,115	58,193	53,244	51,086	54,746

overachieve ment											
Additional reduction due to overachieve ment of NDCs*						4057	4057	4057	2544	2544	2544
Global emissions, including the impact of overachieve ment of NDCs *			56,826	52,592	59,552	52,284	50,059	54,136	50,700	48,542	52,202

* In our assessment, we assumed that countries will follow their current policies emission trajectory if they overachieve their NDC targets, leading to additional net reductions at the global level of 4.6 and 2.8 GtCO₂eq for the unconditional and conditional NDC scenario, respectively.